

g of fresh leaves, in Anand, the highly susceptible check. This trend is reflected in reducing and total sugars as well.

The amount of phenol and sugars present in the leaves of resistant varieties varied considerably, but was always higher than that present in moderately susceptible Bhagalpuri, which in turn was higher than that present in highly susceptible Anand (see table).

These findings establish that higher amounts of phenols and sugars keep BB lesion size smaller by generating a resistant reaction to the BB pathogen. □

Total phenol and reducing and total sugar content in apparently healthy leaves from BB inoculated resistant (R), moderately resistant (MR), and highly susceptible (HS) rice varieties. Kumarganj, India.

Variety	Resistance level ^a	Reaction	Total phenol ^b (mg/100 g)	Reducing sugars ^b (mg/100 g)	Total sugars ^b (g/100 g)
IR20	1	R	278.26	114.40	1.1085
Anjani III	1	R	126.08	113.90	1.1080
Damodar	1	R	121.73	114.30	1.1059
Randhuri	1	R	117.39	114.00	1.1070
Getu	1	R	113.04	114.00	1.1060
Zeerabatti	1	R	113.04	113.90	1.1069
Bishunbhog	1	R	112.50	113.80	1.1058
Bhagalpuri	5	MR	104.34	113.70	1.1050
Anand	9	HS	100.00	113.50	1.1048

^a Standard evaluation system for rice (1980). ^b Fresh weight basis.

Field screening IRRI lines against tungro (RTV) disease in Lanrang

M. Sudjak S., A. Muis, S. Sama, W. Wakman, Agency for Agricultural Research and Development, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops, P. O. Box 173, Ung Pandang, Indonesia

To obtain sources of resistance to RTV for the breeding programs in Indonesia, we screened IRRI lines in the field in Lanrang substation during the 1986 wet monsoon season.

Lines tested were transplanted in 2 rows of 20 hills/row. Susceptible check variety TNI was transplanted between each two rows. All test lines and TNI were transplanted at 20- × 20cm spacing.

The trial was fertilized with urea and triple superphosphate at 90 kg N/ ha and 26 kg P/ ha. RTV symptoms were measured at 4, 6, and 8 wk after

Field screening of IRRI lines against tungro disease in Lanrang, Indonesia.

Line	SES rating		
	4 WT	6 WT	8 WT
IR1352	0	0	1
IR1354-21-2-3-3-2-2	0	0	1
IR31868-64-2-3-3-3	0	1	1
IR11288-B-B-60-1	0	1	3
IR14437-Kn-6-0-0-5-3	0	1	3
IR15864-430-3-1-2-3	0	1	3
IR19743-43-2-3-3	0	1	3
IR1975-5-2-3-1	0	1	3
IR21567-18-3	0	1	3
IR28224-3-2-3-2	0	1	3
IR28228-119-2-3-1-1	0	0	3
IR29692-99-3-2-1	1	1	3
IR31851-96-2-3-2-1	0	1	3
IR35546-2-1-3-2	0	1	3
IR37218-24-2-2	0	1	3
IR38784-137-2-6-6	0	0	3
IR4432-28-5-30Kr-b-Mr-3	0	1	3
IR4432-28-5-40Kr-b-Mr-9	1	3	3
IR18348-36-3-3	1	3	5
IR28128-45-3-3-2	0	3	5
IR29658-69-2-1	1	3	5
IR29925-22-3-3-3	1	3	5
IR31082-48-2-2	1	3	5
IR33450-25-2-1-1-2-2	1	3	5
IR35664-42-1-2-2-2-2	1	3	5

transplanting (WT) on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

Of 400 lines tested, 18 were resistant and 7 moderately resistant (see table). □

Complete slide sets of photos printed in Field problems of tropical rice, revised 1983, are available for purchase at \$50 (less developed country price) or \$60 (developed country price), including airmail postage and handling, from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. No orders for surface mail handling will be accepted.

Manoharsali, neck blast-resistant variety

Y. Rathaiah and G.R. Das, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, Titabar 785630, Assam, India

During the 1986 Jul-Dec season, a severe neck and nodal blast (BI) incidence throughout Assam offered an opportunity to screen rice varieties against neck B1. Infection was assessed

Incidence of neck BI in 5 varieties in Assam, India.

Variety	Disease score ^a
Manoharsali	0
Kmj 1-17-2	0
Biraj	3
IET7251	9
Pusa 2-21	9

^a Standard evaluation system for rice.

on 20 randomly selected hills of 5 promising varieties grown in adjacent plots.

Manoharsali and Kmj 1-17-2 were totally free of neck BI (see table). Manoharsali also showed complete resistance to B1 in farmers' fields. This variety has been grown in Assam for 20 yr.

Kmj 1-17-2 is a derivative of the cross Manoharsali/IR8 and might have inherited resistance from Manoharsali.

Manoharsali also is tolerant of bacterial leaf blight and sheath blight and resistant to brown planthopper. It is susceptible to brown spot.